

SEARCH STRATEGY AND INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SKILLS AS LINKS TO RESEARCH PROFICIENCY AMONG AGRICULTURE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the context of increasing reliance on digital resources, the study sought to provide a comprehensive understanding of how students navigate, access, and utilize information in the research process. This study aimed to assess participants' search strategies and information retrieval skills and their influence on research proficiency using an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. A total of 257 fourth-year students enrolled in Academic Year 2025-2026 were selected using Taro Yamane. Ten participants were selected from the initial sample to gain deeper insights and to shed light on the quantitative findings. Findings revealed that students demonstrated a high level of competence in search strategies, particularly in the use of keywords, Boolean operators, filtering techniques, and utilizing search techniques. Likewise, participants demonstrated proficient information retrieval skills in locating, selecting, accessing, and evaluating online academic resources. Meanwhile, participants demonstrated a very high level of research proficiency. Although both search strategies and information retrieval skills are critical components of research proficiency, the result did not show a statistically significant correlation. Qualitative findings indicated that although participants have technical skills required to develop research proficiency, there are other factors that contribute to developing research proficiency. Factors include, but are not limited to, reading habits; intrinsic motivation; adequate research guidance; continuous learning; integration of artificial intelligence (AI); and peer support. Future researchers may explore other variables that may influence research proficiency and conduct further research on how digital tools, including AI, can be integrated into the research process.

Keywords: *Search Strategy, Information Retrieval Skills, Research Proficiency, AI Integration*

INTRODUCTION

Research plays a vital role in the continuous educative process of lifelong learners, especially students and researchers. This is particularly crucial given that research has become an integral component of the academic and professional requirements for students. Magnaye & Malabarbas (2022) stressed that research is an essential function and component of any educational institution. In agricultural education and practice, research quality and output were not limited to the precise copy of their research output. In an academic setting, proficiency in research among agriculture students is beyond the basic ability of just writing their academic paper. It serves as a representation of comprehensive skills and habits to generate insights and contribute to evidence-based agricultural practices. Ipanaqué-Zapata (2023) states that developing research skills in university students can improve their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities and generate new knowledge.

Agricultural research often extends into specialized subfields, necessitating the use of credible, discipline-specific sources alongside tailored search strategies. For agriculture students who often engage in highly scientific and data-driven literature, these skills are particularly crucial. Most students make use of digital resources daily, in particular electronic sources, which has a positive effect on their search ability and their ability for self-directed learning, according to Ogunbodede & Sawyerr-George (2023).

In light of the increasing academic demands placed on students, particularly in research-oriented programs, the ability to effectively locate, evaluate, and utilize information has become essential. Despite the recognized importance of search strategy and information retrieval skills, there remains a need to better understand how these competencies relate to students' overall research proficiency, especially within the context of agriculture education.

This study aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDG 4: Quality Education, which deals with inclusive and equitable education and encourages continuous development and lifelong learning. Through strengthening agriculture students' research proficiency, this study can add to the overall quality of higher education.

This study seeks to bridge this gap by examining the extent to which these skills influence the research proficiency of agriculture students. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the enhancement of instructional strategies, inform curriculum development, and support the design of targeted interventions aimed at strengthening students' research competencies, thereby fostering more effective and independent researchers in the field of agriculture.

The study was anchored on the Information Literacy Theory of Christine Bruce (1997)

and the Digital Literacy Theory of Paul Gilster (1997). Bruce's (1997) Information Literacy Theory provides the primary lens for understanding how students interact with information throughout the research process. Complementing this, Gilster's (1997) Digital Literacy Theory emphasizes the cognitive and technical skills required to navigate digital environments critically and effectively.

This theory situates search strategy and information retrieval skills within the realities of technology-driven research. As defined by Triawang & Kurniawan (2021), digital literacy is the ability to use digital tools to find, assess, and properly utilize media in everyday life. Gilster's framework therefore reinforces that digitally mediated search and retrieval processes are not merely technical tasks but involve critical thinking and informed decision-making.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the influence of search strategy and information retrieval skills on research proficiency. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' assessment of their search strategy in terms of:
 - 1.1. Keyword searching;
 - 1.2. Boolean operators;
 - 1.3. Filtering search results; and
 - 1.4. Utilizing search techniques?
2. What is the participants' assessment of their information retrieval skills in terms of:
 - 2.1. Locating;
 - 2.2. Accessing;
 - 2.3. Selecting; and
 - 2.4. Evaluating?
3. What is the participants' level of research proficiency?
4. Do the participants search strategies and information retrieval skills significantly influence their research proficiency?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods research design. This design is to elaborate on the quantitative findings by using qualitative methods (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017; ATLAS.ti Team, 2025). The quantitative phase of the study utilized a descriptive-correlational approach to examine the relationship between students' search strategies, information retrieval skills, and research proficiency. A qualitative phase was integrated to shed light and understand the other underlying factors influencing students' research proficiency. The study was conducted at one university in the province of Bukidnon. A total of 257 agriculture students were selected through random sampling; these students were selected because they have already been exposed to research writing. And selected 10 participants from the initial sample to shed light on the quantitative findings.

Researcher-made and modified questionnaires were used as the primary instrument. The questionnaire undergoes a pilot test using Cronbach's alpha. The first section addresses the search strategy, and this part is taken from research tools used by Graciano (2023), Orakpor and Ezekwibe (2025), and Nasir (2024). The second part addresses information retrieval skills and is taken directly from studies done by Temitope (2024) and Akporhonor and Dime (2025). The researcher obtained formal permission to modify the research instruments from the author of the original study. When modifying the research instrument, an attempt was made to keep the same construct and purpose, but adjust the wording, examples, and terminology to suit the agricultural context.

The data gathered were measured using a five-point Likert scale, from 1 (Very Low / Very Low Proficiency) to 5 (Very High / Very High Proficiency), for the purpose of finding the level of agreement given by the participants' responses, or their level of skill. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to assess its validity and reliability in producing consistent results. In addition to the questionnaire, the participants' research proficiency was measured through their research proposal/outline grade. Since grades are part of students' confidential academic records, strict ethical procedures were followed. Formal permission to access academic grades was obtained from the university registrar prior to data collection.

For qualitative components, a semi-structured interview guide was created to explore participants' experiences in greater detail and to help explain the quantitative results. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation were used to describe the participants' skills. Additionally, data gathered from the semi-structured interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the participants' assessment of their search strategy in terms of: Keyword searching, Boolean operators, Filtering search results, and Utilizing search techniques?

Table 1 Summary Table of Participants Assessment of their Search Strategy

Dimensions of Assessment of Search Strategy	<i>M</i>	Description	<i>SD</i>
Keyword Searching	3.87	Often	0.47
Boolean Operators	3.65	Often	0.65
Filtering Search Results	3.96	Often	0.46
Utilizing Search Techniques	4.04	Often	0.48
Overall Assessment of Search Strategy	3.88	Often	0.52

Table 1 presents the summary table of the participants' assessment of their search strategy as generally rated often ($M = 3.88$). Results indicate that the participants often used various searching techniques in navigating online databases and have consistent experiences in using different techniques when searching for information, with an overall mean of 3.88. Velamuri & Kumar (2025) provides direct support for participants frequently using diverse search techniques with consistency in online database navigation.

Across all four dimensions, the majority of participants often utilize various search techniques ($M = 4.04$), indicating that they are able to apply different approaches when navigating information sources. Similarly, participants often engage in filtering search results ($M = 3.96$), which reflects their ability to refine and narrow down information to obtain more relevant results.

Participants also often use keyword searching ($M = 3.87$), showing that they are familiar with identifying and applying appropriate terms when conducting searches. Meanwhile, Boolean operators ($M = 3.65$) received the lowest mean score among the indicators; however, it still falls within the "often" category, indicating that the majority of participants still practice combining search terms using operators.

Research Question 2. What is the participants' assessment of their information retrieval skills in terms of: Locating, Accessing, Selecting, and Evaluating?

Table 2 Summary Table of Participants Assessment of their Information Retrieval Skill

Dimensions of Assessment of Information Retrieval Skills	<i>M</i>	Description	<i>SD</i>
Locating	4.06	Often	0.47
Accessing	3.79	Often	0.69
Selecting	4.09	Often	0.48
Evaluating	4.15	Often	0.48
Overall Assessment of Information Retrieval Skills	4.02	Often	0.47

Table 2 presents the summary table of the participants' assessment of their information retrieval skill, as generally rated often ($M = 4.02$). Therefore, these results show that most participants believe they often engage in the essential processes involved in finding information, consistent with those discussed by Hambarde & Proenca (2023), who suggest that today's methods of information retrieval have evolved into a more user-centered, adaptive, and intelligent process.

Reflects that the majority of participants consistently perform the key processes of information retrieval, such as locating, accessing, selecting, and evaluating, at a frequent level based on their searching experiences. The implications of these highlight that

participants possess a solid foundation in information retrieval, which supports their academic and research-related tasks. Similarly, the study of Otu & Ukaegbu (2024) found that students generally possess a functional level of information retrieval skills, particularly in identifying, accessing, and using relevant academic resources.

Research Question 3. What is the participants' level of research proficiency?

Table 3 Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Research Proficiency

Rating Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
1.00 -1.49	Very High Proficiency	126	49.03
1.50 – 1.99	High Proficiency	111	43.19
2.00 – 2.49	Moderate Proficiency	18	7.00
2.50 – 2.99	Low Proficiency	2	0.78
3.0 and below	Very Low Proficiency	0	0.00
Total			100.0
Overall Mean			1.41
Interpretation			Very High Proficiency
SD			0.33

Table 3 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' level of research proficiency. Data show that the participants' level of research proficiency was very high, as reflected by the overall mean of 1.41.

This reflects that their research outputs consistently meet high academic standards, demonstrating well-developed competencies in conducting and communicating research. This result is supported by DeJesus et al. (2025), who demonstrate a participant's ability to perform at a high level with respect to the timeliness and quality of their work. Supported also by Davidson & Palermo (2015) and Magnaye & Malabarbas (2022), conducting research itself is essential in the development of research-related competencies. This very high level of research proficiency implies that participants possess strong foundational skills necessary for academic success and the conduct of scholarly work.

Research Question 4. Do the participants search strategies and information retrieval skills significantly influence their research proficiency?

Table 4 Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants Search Strategies and Information Retrieval on their Research Proficiency

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.404	.185		7.569	.881
Search Strategies	.040	.082	.056	.490	.625
Information Retrieval Skills	-.038	.080	-.054	-.470	.639

Model Summary

R = .032 R² = .001 Adjusted R² = .007 F (2,253) = .126 p = .881

*** significant at 0.01 level*

Table 4 presents the results of a regression analysis conducted to determine the influence of participants' search strategies and information retrieval on their research proficiency. Data show that the model was found not significant ($F=2,253$)=.126 $p=.881$, indicating that search strategy and information retrieval did not significantly influence the students' research proficiency, indicating the non-rejection of the null hypothesis. This result confirms the study of Bacarrisas (2023) that enhancing students' academic research skills requires not only the development of technical competencies but also the strengthening of their confidence and motivation in using these skills. Even if the students demonstrate adequate competencies in constructing search strategies or accessing information, these skills do not translate into improved research proficiency.

The lack of a statistically significant relationship between search strategies, information retrieval skills, and research proficiency led the researcher to further explore the findings through a qualitative approach. Although the quantitative results did not show a direct influence, it implies that other underlying factors may influence students' research proficiency.

Across the participants' narratives, it is found out that research proficiency appears to be shaped not by a single dominant factor, but by a dynamic and interrelated combination of influences. These include critical thinking, strategies, reading habits, intrinsic motivation, adviser guidance, continuous learning, societal relevance, AI integration, and peer support. With this, research proficiency develops gradually through practice, reflection, and repeated exposure to research tasks, rather than being determined by one isolated variable.

The participants' experience implies that research proficiency is both a personal and a social activity. On one hand, a participant's development of research proficiency was

influenced by internal motivators. However, the strengthened external supports, such as mentorship, collaboration, and access to digital tools, make information gathering and analysis more efficient. In this sense, research proficiency may be better understood as an evolving capability built through the interaction of cognitive skills, affective factors, and learning environments.

Conclusions

The findings of this study indicate that participants have developed a high level of competence in search strategies, particularly in the use of keywords, Boolean operators, filtering of search results, and utilizing search techniques. Participants demonstrated the ability to construct effective search queries and refine results to obtain more accurate and relevant information. These searching skills go beyond the mere application of techniques; rather, they play a critical role in enabling students to efficiently locate and gather information necessary for research writing.

Additionally, participants have shown to possess good information retrieval skills. The participants were able to locate, select, access, and evaluate online resources. In part due to their knowledge of different digital platforms and academic databases, they were able to locate credible online materials. Good information retrieval skills require both technical competence and an understanding of strategic awareness available during the search process. Therefore, this indicates that the students have acquired sufficient skills to operate within a digital academic environment where the ability to manage information is essential.

Although the participants' information retrieval skills and search strategies were high, the statistical data showed that there was no significant influence between search strategies and information retrieval skills and research proficiency. A student's level of technical skill does not guarantee that they are proficient in research. However, technical skill provides the foundation upon which a student can build and develop successful research skills. Further implications of the study show that research proficiency is determined and influenced by various factors beyond simply having access to information. Other factors such as reading practices, guidance from research advisers, continuous learning, the perceived relevance of their study to the community, and peer support may play a significant role in shaping overall research proficiency.

Recommendations

In light of the findings that participants demonstrate high competence in search strategies and information retrieval skills, yet show no significant relationship between these skills and overall research proficiency, several recommendations are proposed:

1. University administrators are encouraged to strengthen institutional support for research development through allocating resources for workshops that emphasize critical thinking, academic writing, and data analysis; establishing a research-supportive environment can help bridge the gap between technical competence and actual research performance.

2. The library administrator may initiate advanced information literacy workshops or research strategy clinics that focus on critical evaluation, identifying relevance, and synthesizing information. And strengthen collaborative partnerships with faculty to ensure that library instruction is closely aligned with the actual research demands in the classroom, thereby making it more relevant, integrated, and responsive to students' academic needs.
3. Faculty may collaborate with librarians to ensure that research training is consistent, guided, and aligned with course requirements.
4. Students are encouraged to maximize their existing strengths in searching and retrieving information by actively developing higher-order research skills. This includes engaging in extensive reading, practicing critical analysis and synthesis of sources, and seeking guidance from research advisers and peers.
5. Future researchers may explore other variables that could influence research proficiency, such as critical thinking skills, writing competence, motivation, and the role of academic support systems. Employing different research designs or expanding the sample size and context may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting research performance. Additionally, further studies may examine how digital tools, including AI, can be effectively integrated into the research process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares that this research study was conducted in full adherence to established ethical standards and academic integrity. Ethical clearance was first obtained from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee. A formal letter requesting permission to conduct a study was sent to the university president. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, and they were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, as well as their right to voluntarily participate and withdraw at any time without any consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained throughout the research process by ensuring that no identifying information was collected and that all data were coded and reported in aggregate form. Data privacy principles were rigorously observed, with all collected information securely stored and accessible only to the researcher. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded at all times, with no known risks associated with their participation in the study. Furthermore, this research was conducted with no conflict of interest, and all findings were interpreted objectively and without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly cited and acknowledged. The results of this study are used solely for academic and research purposes. Any use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the development of this paper has been appropriately disclosed and utilized responsibly to support, but not replace, the author's original work and analysis.

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